

Original Research

The Effects of Cryptocurrency on Investment Portfolio in Tanzania: A Case of Cryptocurrency Brokers at Yellow Card Company

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Abstract

This study investigated the effects of cryptocurrency on investment portfolios through currency brokers at Yellow Card Company in Tanzania, focusing on price fluctuations, volatility metrics, and market swings. A cross-sectional research design was chosen to capture a snapshot of broker and investor experiences at a specific moment, allowing for a comprehensive analysis of current practices and attitudes. This design is particularly effective in understanding relationships between variables in a relatively short timeframe, making it ideal for exploring the dynamic cryptocurrency market. Utilizing a quantitative approach, data were collected from 43 brokers and investors through structured questionnaires, enabling statistical analysis and robust conclusions. Analysis conducted with IBM SPSS Version 26 revealed that while price fluctuations positively impacted broker returns, this effect was statistically insignificant. In contrast, high volatility metrics significantly negatively affected returns, while market swings exhibited a positive but insignificant effect. These findings underscore the substantial risks posed by cryptocurrency volatility, adversely impacting broker returns despite potential diversification benefits. The study concludes that effective risk management strategies are essential for mitigating these negative impacts. Recommendations for brokers and investors include the implementation of advanced risk management techniques and the establishment of regulatory frameworks to mitigate risks associated with cryptocurrency investments in emerging economies. This research enriches practical insights and emphasizes the significance of volatility in the management of investment portfolios in the context of cryptocurrency.

Keywords: Cryptocurrency, Investment, Portfolio.

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Introduction

Cryptocurrency markets have experienced significant volatility since the introduction of Bitcoin in 2008 by the pseudonymous Satoshi Nakamoto. This digital currency, like many others, has been integrated into investment portfolios globally, with investors seeking diversification and high returns. The rapid price fluctuations of cryptocurrencies, such as Bitcoin and Ethereum, have made them attractive yet risky assets (Gandal et al., 2022; Nakamoto, 2008). In developed countries, regulatory frameworks and institutional participation have enabled investors to incorporate cryptocurrencies into their portfolios more securely. This has opened opportunities for potentially enhanced returns while also exposing investors to high volatility and associated risks (European Central Bank, 2012; Grinberg, 2012).

In Africa, cryptocurrency adoption varies widely, with some countries embracing it while others impose restrictions. Nigeria, for example, has witnessed a surge in cryptocurrency usage despite a lack of comprehensive regulations (Central Bank of Nigeria, 2021). African markets generally lack the regulatory structures seen in developed nations, creating both opportunities and challenges for investors. Cryptocurrencies have been used for remittances and hedging against local currency volatility, making them an appealing alternative to traditional assets (Letho et al., 2022). However, the absence of a robust legal framework raises concerns about the sustainability of these investments in African portfolios (Boiko et al., 2021).

East African countries are witnessing a growing interest in cryptocurrency, particularly in Kenya and Uganda, where digital currencies are being adopted for investment and remittance purposes. Kenya, with its advanced mobile payment systems, has emerged as a leader in cryptocurrency activity, while Uganda is gradually embracing these technologies for cross-border transactions and as a hedge against inflation (Wangui, 2023). However, regulatory frameworks remain underdeveloped across the region. Governments, including those of Kenya, Uganda, and Tanzania, have voiced concerns about the risks associated with cryptocurrencies, including fraud and money laundering (Njoroge & Oketch, 2023). Despite these concerns, the potential for cryptocurrencies to enhance financial inclusion and stimulate economic growth remains a driving force behind their adoption in East Africa.

In Tanzania, the adoption of cryptocurrency is growing, but challenges persist, especially regarding regulation and investor protection. While cryptocurrencies are gaining traction as an investment alternative, the Bank of Tanzania (BOT) continues to express concerns over the lack of legal oversight and potential risks to investors (BOT, 2018, 2019). In 2023, the BOT reiterated its warnings about the dangers posed by digital currencies, including susceptibility to fraud and lack of buyer protection in case of disputes. Many investors, especially those who are not technologically savvy, face significant challenges navigating these risks without a robust legal framework in place (BOT, 2024). Despite these challenges, some businesses and individuals have embraced cryptocurrencies, seeing them as a way to diversify portfolios or engage in cross-border transactions without the delays and fees associated with traditional banking systems. However, this enthusiasm is tempered by reported cases of fraud, with the Tanzania

Financial Intelligence Unit noting a sharp increase in cryptocurrency-related fraud cases in 2023. Many of these cases involved fake exchanges and Ponzi schemes that targeted unsuspecting investors (Tanzania Financial Intelligence Unit, 2023). Furthermore, the fluctuating value of cryptocurrencies poses additional challenges for investors, who must contend with volatile markets. Without regulatory guidance and adequate consumer protection laws, cryptocurrency investors in Tanzania remain vulnerable to significant financial losses. Consequently, the BOT has called for more comprehensive legislation to mitigate these risks, while still allowing room for innovation and financial inclusion (Komba, 2023). This situation underscores the importance of further research into the effects of cryptocurrency volatility on investment portfolios in Tanzania, as more individuals and businesses explore this evolving digital financial landscape.

This study investigates the effects of cryptocurrency on investment portfolios, focusing on price fluctuations, volatility metrics, and market swings among brokers at Yellow Card Company. The general objective is to assess how cryptocurrency volatility affects portfolio performance and risk management. Price fluctuations, one of the most common challenges, require brokers to make frequent adjustments to protect their portfolios. Volatility metrics are crucial for informed decision-making, guiding when to buy or sell assets, while market swings often lead to reassessments of risk exposure. Modern Portfolio Theory (MPT), which emphasizes diversification to mitigate risk, provides a theoretical foundation for the study (Markowitz, 1952). MPT's application in this context helps explain how cryptocurrency's high volatility influences investment strategies. Recent studies have also highlighted the need for empirical evidence on how price fluctuations and volatility impact broker returns, particularly in emerging markets like Tanzania (Ochieng & Wangari, 2023). By filling this gap, the study addresses both practical and theoretical concerns regarding cryptocurrency's role in portfolio management.

Literature Review

Theoretical Review

Risk-Return Trade-Off Models

The Risk-Return Trade-Off model is a foundational concept in finance, established by Harry Markowitz in 1952, and later expanded by theorists such as Sharpe in the 1960s. The model posits that the potential return on an investment increase with the level of risk associated with it, meaning investors must balance the desire for high returns with the acceptance of higher risk (Markowitz, 1952; Sharpe, 1964). The theory suggests that different assets carry varying levels of risk and return, and the combination of these assets into a portfolio can optimize returns for a given level of risk. This theory applies directly to the study of cryptocurrency investments, where price fluctuations, volatility, and market swings introduce significant risks, yet offer the potential for substantial returns. The study aims to explore how brokers manage this risk-return trade-off when dealing with cryptocurrencies.

In this study, the Risk-Return Trade-Off model provides a framework for understanding how cryptocurrency brokers at Yellow Card Company balance risk and

return in their portfolios. Price fluctuations and market volatility, as highlighted in the study, represent the high-risk environment of cryptocurrencies, and the theory helps explain how brokers might seek to mitigate these risks while still aiming for high returns. The strength of this theory lies in its applicability to volatile markets like cryptocurrency, where investors must frequently adjust their portfolios to manage risk. By using the Risk-Return Trade-Off model, the study can assess how brokers optimize their portfolios in response to market swings, ultimately contributing to a better understanding of cryptocurrency's role in investment strategies (Jiang et al., 2023; Zhang & Liu, 2024).

Empirical Review

Cryptocurrency from Developing Economies

A study by Gandal et al., (2022) aimed to assess the impact of cryptocurrency volatility on investment diversification. By using quantitative analysis of historical cryptocurrency price data and portfolio simulations, the researchers found that integrating cryptocurrencies into diversified investment portfolios both enhanced returns and reduced risk, particularly due to their low correlation with traditional assets. The study concluded that while cryptocurrencies introduced volatility, their inclusion could strategically lower overall portfolio risk. These findings are relevant to this study as they provide empirical evidence on how cryptocurrency fluctuations affect portfolio performance, supporting the examination of volatility impacts on broker returns in Tanzania.

Then, study by Letho et al., (2022) investigated the use of cryptocurrencies as a hedge against currency volatility in emerging markets, with a focus on African countries. Employing econometric models to analyze the relationship between cryptocurrency returns and local currency fluctuations, the researchers discovered that cryptocurrencies could effectively hedge against local currency volatility, offering potential stability in otherwise unstable economic environments. The study recommended incorporating cryptocurrencies into investment strategies to mitigate currency risk. This research was pertinent to the current study as it highlighted the role of cryptocurrencies in managing economic risks, aligning with the exploration of how cryptocurrency volatility affected investment portfolios in Tanzania.

And, study by (Ermek, 2021) explored diversification strategies and risk management practices in cryptocurrency markets. By utilizing a comparative analysis of various cryptocurrency portfolios and their performance metrics, the study found that cryptocurrencies provided significant opportunities for diversification due to their distinct risk-return profiles. However, it also highlighted the challenges posed by high volatility. The study concluded that effective risk management strategies were essential for leveraging cryptocurrencies' diversification benefits. This research supported the current study by providing insights into how cryptocurrencies impacted portfolio risk management and performance, particularly in the context of high volatility affecting broker returns in Tanzania.

Cryptocurrency from Developed Economies

A study by Liu and Tsyvinski (2021) from Yale University examined the risk and return characteristics of cryptocurrency markets in the context of developed economies. Using extensive time-series data, they found that Bitcoin and other major cryptocurrencies exhibit unique risk-return trade-offs that are distinct from traditional financial assets like stocks or bonds. Their findings suggest that cryptocurrencies offer both high risk and high return, making them a potential asset class for diversification in portfolios with a higher risk tolerance. This study provides a foundation for understanding how cryptocurrencies can function in portfolios, especially in volatile markets like Tanzania's cryptocurrency scene.

And, Corbet et al. (2020) conducted a comprehensive analysis on the volatility dynamics of cryptocurrencies in developed financial markets. Using GARCH (Generalized Autoregressive Conditional Heteroskedasticity) models, they demonstrated that cryptocurrency returns are significantly more volatile than traditional assets, but this volatility could be managed through sophisticated risk management techniques. Their research underscores the importance of dynamic risk management strategies for portfolio optimization when dealing with cryptocurrencies. These findings align with the current study, emphasizing the role of volatility metrics in influencing broker returns in Tanzania's evolving cryptocurrency market.

Study Gap

This study on the effects of cryptocurrency on investment portfolios in Tanzania highlights several practical, theoretical, and contextual gaps based on previous research. The practical gap in this study stems from the limited application of cryptocurrency investment strategies within the Tanzanian context. While studies such as Gandal et al. (2022) and Letho et al. (2022) have explored the role of cryptocurrencies in diversified portfolios and as hedges against volatility in various global markets, their findings do not fully address the unique challenges faced by Tanzanian brokers. Practical issues like regulatory uncertainty, limited technological infrastructure, and a nascent cryptocurrency ecosystem make it difficult to apply global best practices in Tanzania. This study fills that gap by focusing on the actual experiences of cryptocurrency brokers at Yellow Card Company in Tanzania, who face different operational challenges compared to their counterparts in more developed financial markets.

Theoretical gaps emerge from the application of existing models like Modern Portfolio Theory (MPT) or the Risk-Return Trade-Off Model, which have been extensively utilized in developed economies but are less frequently tested within developing contexts like Tanzania. Previous studies, such as Corbet et al. (2020) and Ermek (2021), primarily apply these models to general financial markets, but do not address their limitations when applied to cryptocurrency, especially in environments with less financial infrastructure and regulatory oversight. By exploring how these theoretical frameworks hold in Tanzania's nascent cryptocurrency sector, this study contributes to understanding the robustness and applicability of these theories in a different financial ecosystem.

The context and geographical gap are evident in the fact that much of the existing literature focuses on cryptocurrency markets in developed economies or regions such as the US, Europe, or Asia. Few studies explore the dynamics of cryptocurrency investment in African economies, particularly Tanzania. Studies like Letho et al. (2022) have touched on emerging markets, but specific research on how cryptocurrency impacts investment portfolios in Tanzania remains limited. This study, therefore, bridges the geographical gap by focusing on a less-explored region, providing valuable insights into cryptocurrency volatility in the Tanzanian context.

Conceptual Framework

Figure1. Conceptual Framework

The conceptual framework of this study examines how cryptocurrency market dynamics, specifically price fluctuations, volatility metrics, and market swings, influence the investment portfolio performance of brokers in Tanzania. These independent variables are essential in assessing the effects of cryptocurrency on portfolio returns, as brokers rely on volatility metrics and market trends to make informed decisions. Broker returns serve as indicator of the dependent variable, representing the overall performance of investment portfolios. By analyzing how these factors interact, this study aims to identify strategies that brokers can adopt to manage cryptocurrency-related risks while maximizing portfolio returns. The framework bridges theoretical models, such as Modern Portfolio Theory and the Risk-Return Trade-Off, with empirical insights, focusing on the specific challenges and opportunities faced by Tanzanian cryptocurrency brokers, providing a localized perspective on a global financial phenomenon.

Methodology

This study adopted a cross-sectional research design and a quantitative approach to examine how cryptocurrency market volatility impacts the investment portfolios of brokers at Yellow Card Company in Tanzania. The cross-sectional design was chosen to capture the effects of price fluctuations, volatility metrics, and market swings on portfolio performance at a specific point in time, offering a real-time snapshot of market dynamics. The quantitative approach allowed for statistical analysis, ensuring objectivity in measuring the relationship between independent and dependent variables. This design was considered more appropriate than longitudinal approaches due to the focus on

immediate investment behaviors within a volatile and fast-changing cryptocurrency market.

The study's population comprised 108 investors and brokers actively involved in cryptocurrency trading at Yellow Card Company during 2023/2024. A purposive sampling method was employed to select 50 respondents with significant exposure to cryptocurrency investments, ensuring relevance to the research objectives. Out of the selected respondents, 43 valid responses were obtained for analysis. The choice to focus on a single platform, Yellow Card, reflects its prominence in cryptocurrency trading within Tanzania, although this introduces limitations in generalizing findings to other platforms or the broader market. Despite this, the sample size was adequate for the statistical analyses undertaken, allowing for an insightful examination of the research variables.

Data collection was carried out using structured questionnaires, which were pilot-tested for reliability and validity. The questionnaire featured closed-ended questions and a Likert scale to capture detailed information on price fluctuations, volatility metrics, and market swings. The tool was pilot-tested with a small subset of respondents, resulting in a Cronbach's alpha of above 0.7, indicating good internal consistency and reliability. This ensured that the data collection instrument was robust enough to gather accurate and comprehensive data from respondents, while maintaining the reliability of measurements.

Data analysis was conducted using IBM SPSS Version 26, employing descriptive statistics to summarize the data, and Pearson correlation to assess relationships between variables. The study used an Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) regression model to evaluate the effects of independent variables (price fluctuations, volatility metrics, and market swings) on the dependent variable (investment portfolio performance, measured by broker returns). The OLS regression was chosen for its ability to handle continuous variables and estimate linear relationships. However, recognizing the potential non-normality in some variables, future research may consider using generalized linear models (GLM) to account for any skewness and enhance the robustness of the findings. The regression model used is specified as:

$$Y = \beta_0 + \beta_1X_1 + \beta_2X_2 + \beta_3X_4 + \epsilon \quad (1)$$

Measurement of Variables

From equation 1 in this study, the variables are defined and measured as follows:

Price Fluctuations (X_1): Price fluctuations refer to the degree of variation in cryptocurrency prices over a certain period. This is measured by calculating the percentage change in the closing prices of selected cryptocurrencies, such as Bitcoin and Ethereum, over a defined time frame (e.g., daily, weekly, or monthly). Historical price data is sourced from cryptocurrency exchanges and analyzed to quantify these fluctuations. A higher variation indicates greater price volatility, which is critical in understanding the effect on investment portfolios.

Volatility Metrics (X_2): Volatility is measured using standard financial metrics such as the standard deviation of cryptocurrency returns over a specific period. It represents the

degree of variation in returns and serves as an indicator of market risk. In this study, volatility is calculated using historical price data for the selected cryptocurrencies, with high volatility values signifying greater uncertainty and risk in the market.

Market Swings (X_3): Market swings refer to large and often unexpected shifts in cryptocurrency prices, which can significantly impact investment decisions. These are measured by analyzing major price movements, often triggered by market events or news. The magnitude and frequency of these swings are assessed using data from cryptocurrency markets to understand their influence on portfolio performance.

Investment Portfolio Performance (Y): The dependent variable, broker returns, is used as an indicator of investment portfolio performance. Broker returns are measured by the actual percentage gain or loss in the value of a broker's cryptocurrency portfolio over a defined period. This is derived from transaction data and portfolio valuations, providing insight into the overall effectiveness of the broker's investment strategy in the context of cryptocurrency market conditions.

These measurements collectively contribute to understanding how cryptocurrency market dynamics influence investment outcomes.

Validity and Reliability of the Study

The validity of this study is ensured through multiple forms: content validity, construct validity, criterion-related validity, and face validity. Content validity was established by developing the questionnaire with input from experts and the supervisor, ensuring that the items accurately reflect the constructs of price fluctuations, volatility metrics, and market swings. Construct validity was assessed through factor analysis to confirm that the questions align with theoretical expectations. Criterion-related validity was evaluated using correlations between the questionnaire responses and relevant performance metrics of investment portfolios. Finally, face validity was checked by ensuring the questionnaire appeared logical and relevant to the respondents. A pilot study was conducted, including a retest of the questionnaire to enhance reliability before full data collection commenced (Tavakol & Dennick, 2011).

Table 1. Reliability Statistics

Cronbach's Alpha	Cronbach's Alpha Based on Standardized Items	N of Items
.889	.894	15

While, the reliability of the study's questionnaire was assessed using Cronbach's Alpha, yielding a value of 0.889, indicating high internal consistency among the 15 items measured. When adjusted for standardized items, the Cronbach's Alpha slightly increased to 0.894. These results suggest that the questionnaire is a reliable tool for measuring the constructs of price fluctuations, volatility metrics, and market swings in relation to investment portfolio performance. A Cronbach's Alpha value above 0.7 is generally considered acceptable, while values above 0.8 are deemed excellent, affirming the

robustness of the measurement instrument used in this study (Middleton, 2020; Surucu & Maslakci, 2020).

Findings and discussions

Demographic Profile of the Respondents

Table 2. Response Rate and Demographic of Respondents (n=43)

	Frequency	Percent (%)
Response	43	86.0
No Response	7	14.0
Total	50	100
Gender		
Male	25	58.1
Female	18	41.9
Age Group Distribution		
18 - 35 Years Old	23	53.5
36 - 55 Years Old	16	37.2
56 Years Old and above	4	9.3
Education Level Qualification		
Diploma and below	17	39.5
Bachelor Degree	23	53.5
Master's Degree and above	3	7.0
Experience in Cryptocurrency		
Less than a year	22	51.2
1-5 Years	17	39.5
6-10 Years	3	7.0
11 Years and above	1	2.3

The demographic findings, summarized in Table 2, reveal critical insights into the respondent profile. A total of 50 participants were approached, with an impressive response rate of 86% (43 respondents), indicating strong engagement with the survey. Gender distribution shows a slight male predominance, with males accounting for 58.1% and females at 41.9%. Age-wise, the study captures a youthful demographic, with 53.5% of respondents aged 18-35 years, suggesting that younger individuals are more likely to explore cryptocurrency investments. Regarding education levels, a majority (53.5%) hold bachelor's degrees, reflecting a potentially higher financial literacy essential for navigating the complexities of cryptocurrency. Finally, experience in cryptocurrency is notable, with 51.2% of participants having less than a year of involvement, suggesting that the market in Tanzania may still be in its early adoption stages. This demographic insight is pivotal for understanding the study's context, particularly how the characteristics of respondents can influence their investment behaviors and portfolio performance in the cryptocurrency landscape.

Descriptive Statistics

Price Fluctuations

Table 3. Price Fluctuations of Crypto currency on Broker Return in investment portfolio (n=43)

Statements	N	Min	Max	Mean	Std. Deviation
Crypto currency price fluctuations influence my investments.	43	2.00	5.00	4.1163	.82258
Managing crypto price changes is challenging.	43	2.00	5.00	3.9767	.85880
Crypto price volatility strongly affects portfolio's performance.	43	2.00	5.00	3.1628	.87097
Unpredictable crypto price swings prompt portfolio adjustments.	43	2.00	5.00	3.6512	.86969
Crypto market volatility poses high investment risk.	43	2.00	5.00	4.4651	.66722

The findings in Table 3 underscore the significant impact of cryptocurrency price fluctuations on brokers' investment decisions. With a high mean of 4.12 for the statement "Crypto currency price fluctuations influence my investments," brokers express strong recognition of the influence of price changes on their strategies. Similarly, the mean of 4.47 for "Crypto market volatility poses high investment risk" indicates an awareness of the inherent risks associated with crypto investments. The mean score of 3.98 for "Managing crypto price changes is challenging" highlights the difficulties brokers face in adapting to market shifts. Furthermore, a mean of 3.65 for "Unpredictable crypto price swings prompt portfolio adjustments" suggests that brokers actively adjust their strategies in response to sudden price movements. However, the mean of 3.16 for "Crypto price volatility strongly affects portfolio's performance" indicates a slightly less pronounced belief in volatility's direct effect on performance, suggesting a need for further analysis to understand the nuances of these relationships. Overall, the results demonstrate the critical role that price fluctuations play in shaping brokers' investment behaviors and highlight the complexities involved in navigating the volatile cryptocurrency market.

Market Volatility Measures

Table 4. Market Volatility Measures on Broker Return in investment portfolio (n=43)

Statements	N	Min	Max	Mean	Std. Deviation
Use volatility metrics for assessment	43	1.00	5.00	3.6047	1.15757
Volatility metrics inform my buy/sell decisions.	43	1.00	5.00	3.4186	1.02893
High volatility deters from increasing holdings.	43	1.00	5.00	3.5116	1.05497
Volatility metrics are crucial for assessing returns.	43	1.00	5.00	3.0465	.87160
Risk management relies on volatility metrics.	43	1.00	5.00	3.3256	1.20950

The findings in Table 4 reveal brokers' perspectives on the role of volatility metrics in influencing their investment decisions. The mean score of 3.60 for the statement "Use volatility metrics for assessment" indicates a strong recognition of the importance of these metrics in evaluating market conditions. Similarly, a mean of 3.42 for "Volatility metrics inform my buy/sell decisions" reflects a substantial reliance on volatility data when making trading choices. The score of 3.51 for "High volatility deters from increasing holdings" further suggests that brokers perceive volatility as a deterrent to expanding their investment positions. However, the lower mean of 3.05 for "Volatility metrics are crucial for assessing returns" indicates some ambivalence about their role in return assessment. Lastly, a mean of 3.33 for "Risk management relies on volatility metrics" confirms the necessity of these metrics in shaping risk management strategies. Overall, these results highlight the essential role that volatility metrics play in brokers' investment processes, indicating that while they are utilized, there may be room for enhancing their integration into decision-making frameworks.

Market Swings Fluctuations

Table 5. Market Swings Fluctuations on Broker Return in investment portfolio (n=43)

Statements	N	Min	Max	Mean	Std. Deviation
Promptly adjust investment strategy as needed.	43	1.00	5.00	3.2791	1.29699
React to sharp price movements to protect portfolio.	43	1.00	5.00	3.0000	1.21499
Reassess risk exposure during significant market swings.	43	1.00	5.00	2.9535	1.17420
Large price shifts impact portfolio performance.	43	1.00	5.00	3.0233	1.18499
Extreme market swings affect investment confidence.	43	2.00	5.00	3.7209	.85428

The findings in Table 5 illustrate brokers' attitudes toward adjusting their investment strategies in response to market swings. The average score for the statement "Promptly adjust investment strategy as needed" is 3.28, indicating a moderate inclination to adapt. However, the mean score for "Reassess risk exposure during significant market swings" is notably lower at 2.95, reflecting a reluctance to engage in proactive risk management. This hesitance is further emphasized by the mean score of 3.00 for "React to sharp price movements to protect portfolio," suggesting that brokers may be cautious in their responses to immediate market changes. The higher score of 3.72 for "Extreme market swings affect investment confidence" underscores the psychological impact of volatility on brokers' decision-making processes. These results highlight the need for further investigation into the factors influencing brokers' hesitance, particularly focusing on psychological barriers, lack of experience, and emotional biases, which can hinder timely and effective responses to market fluctuations.

Inferential Statistics

Normality Distribution of Data

Table 6 presents the normality distribution of data, showing that skewness and kurtosis values for the independent variables (Price Fluctuations, Volatility Metrics, and Market Swings) are close to zero, indicating relatively normal distributions. Price Fluctuations and Market Swings show slight negative skewness, while Volatility Metrics also display a mild negative skew, suggesting that data slightly leans towards higher values.

Table 6. Skewness and Kurtosis Normality Distribution of Data

		Statistic	Std. Error
Price Fluctuations	Mean	3.8744	.05569
	Kurtosis	-.052	.709
Volatility Metrics	Mean	3.3814	.07163
	Skewness	-.253	.361
	Kurtosis	-.428	.709
Market Swings	Mean	3.1953	.06225
	Skewness	-.355	.361
	Kurtosis	-.500	.709
Broker Return in Investment Portfolio	Mean	1.1628	.05696
	Skewness	1.894	.361
	Kurtosis	1.661	.709

Broker Return, the dependent variable, exhibits a strong positive skew (Skewness = 1.894) and positive kurtosis (Kurtosis = 1.661), indicating a non-normal distribution with data clustering towards lower values. This skewness suggests that broker returns in investment portfolios are more concentrated at the lower end of the distribution.

The normality tests in Table 7 reveal key insights about the study variables. The dependent variable, Broker Return in Investment Portfolio, shows significant non-normality in both the Kolmogorov-Smirnov and Shapiro-Wilk tests ($p = .000$), indicating a non-normal distribution. This is consistent with the skewness and kurtosis findings.

Table 6. Tests of Normality

	Kolmogorov-Smirnov ^a			Shapiro-Wilk		
	Statistic	Df	Sig.	Statistic	df	Sig.
Price Fluctuations	.146	43	.022	.937	43	.021
Volatility Metrics	.144	43	.025	.962	43	.161
Market Swings	.134	43	.051	.955	43	.088
Broker Return in Investment Portfolio	.506	43	.000	.445	43	.000

a. Lilliefors Significance Correction

Among the independent variables, Price Fluctuations also display significant deviations from normality ($p < .05$). However, Volatility Metrics and Market Swings do not significantly deviate from normality ($p > .05$ in the Shapiro-Wilk test), suggesting that these two independent variables are normally distributed, making them more suitable for parametric analysis.

Non-Parametric Test

Given the findings from the normality tests, dependent variable (Broker Return) shows significant non-normality. This suggests that non-parametric analysis may be more appropriate for analyzing broker returns, as parametric tests typically assume normal distribution of data. However, since some of independent variables (Volatility Metrics and Market Swings) are normally distributed, study might consider a combination of both parametric and non-parametric methods. The study used non-parametric tests (the Mann-Whitney U test) for variables that violate normality, while applying parametric tests (OLS regression analysis) for those that meet the normality assumption. This mixed approach can ensure accurate analysis given the characteristics of your data.

The Mann-Whitney U Test

Table 8. The Mann-Whitney U Test

	Null Hypothesis	Test	Sig.	Decision
1	The distribution of Price Fluctuations is the same across categories of Broker Return in Investment Portfolio.	Independent-Samples Mann-Whitney U Test	.112 ^a	Retain the null hypothesis.
2	The distribution of Volatility Metrics is the same across categories of Broker Return in Investment Portfolio.	Independent-Samples Mann-Whitney U Test	.166 ^a	Retain the null hypothesis.
3	The distribution of Market Swings is the same across categories of Broker Return in Investment Portfolio.	Independent-Samples Mann-Whitney U Test	.323 ^a	Retain the null hypothesis.
Asymptotic significances are displayed. The significance level is .050.				
a. Exact significance is displayed for this test.				

Table 8 presents the results of the Mann-Whitney U Test, examining the distribution of independent variables—price fluctuations, volatility metrics, and market swings—across categories of broker return in investment portfolios. The results indicate that all three independent variables retained the null hypothesis, with significance levels of 0.112, 0.166, and 0.323, respectively. This suggests that there is no statistically significant difference in the distributions of these factors concerning broker returns, implying that market conditions may not influence brokers' performance as expected. Consequently, further analysis is warranted to explore potential correlations among these variables using Spearman's correlation coefficient, as it is suitable for assessing relationships in non-normally distributed data, which is often the case in financial contexts.

Correlation Analysis

Table 9 displays the Spearman's correlation coefficients between broker returns in investment portfolios and the independent variables of price fluctuations, volatility metrics, and market swings. Notably, there is a significant negative correlation between broker returns and volatility metrics ($r = -0.309$, $p = 0.043$), suggesting that higher volatility may negatively impact broker performance. Conversely, price fluctuations exhibited a positive but non-significant correlation ($r = 0.218$, $p = 0.161$), indicating a potential but weak relationship. The market swings variable showed no significant correlation with broker returns ($r = 0.112$, $p = 0.475$). These findings highlight the need for brokers to manage volatility effectively, as it can directly influence investment performance, aligning with prior research emphasizing the importance of risk management in volatile markets.

Table 7. Correlations

			Broker Return in Investment Portfolio	Price Fluctuations	Volatility Metrics	Market Swings
Spearman's rho	Broker Return in Investment Portfolio	Correlation Coefficient	1.000	.218	-.309*	.112
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.	.161	.043	.475
		N	43	43	43	43
	Price Fluctuations	Correlation Coefficient	.218	1.000	.209	.121
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.161	.	.178	.440
		N	43	43	43	43
	Volatility Metrics	Correlation Coefficient	-.309*	.209	1.000	.276
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.043	.178	.	.073
		N	43	43	43	43
	Market Swings	Correlation Coefficient	.112	.121	.276	1.000
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.475	.440	.073	.
		N	43	43	43	43

*. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

Regression Analysis

Model Summary Analysis

Table 10. Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.438 ^a	.192	.130	.34840
a. Predictors: (Constant), Market Swings, Price Fluctuations, Volatility Metrics				
b. Dependent Variable: Broker Return in Investment Portfolio				

The results in Table 10 indicate a moderate relationship between the independent variables (Market Swings, Price Fluctuations, and Volatility Metrics) and the dependent variable, Broker Return in Investment Portfolio. The R value of 0.438 suggests a moderate correlation, indicating that changes in these market conditions have some influence on broker returns. The R² value of 0.192 implies that approximately 19.2% of the variability in broker returns can be explained by these factors. However, the adjusted R² of 0.130 indicates that the model's explanatory power is somewhat limited, revealing that other variables likely play a significant role in determining broker returns that are not included in this analysis. This highlights the need for further investigation into additional factors influencing investment performance in the cryptocurrency market, emphasizing the complexity of financial behaviors in this evolving field.

Analysis of Variance

Table 11. ANOVA

	Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	1.127	3	.376	3.094	.038 ^b
	Residual	4.734	39	.121		
	Total	5.860	42			
a. Dependent Variable: Broker Return in Investment Portfolio						
b. Predictors: (Constant), Market Swings, Price Fluctuations, Volatility Metrics						

The analysis of variance (ANOVA) results presented in Table 11 demonstrate the significance of the regression model predicting Broker Return in Investment Portfolio, with an F-value of 3.094 and a p-value of 0.038. This indicates that at least one of the independent variables—Market Swings, Price Fluctuations, or Volatility Metrics—has a statistically significant impact on broker returns. The sum of squares for regression is 1.127, suggesting that these variables explain a meaningful portion of the variance in broker returns. The residual sum of squares (4.734) shows the unexplained variability, highlighting the importance of considering other potential factors affecting investment performance in the cryptocurrency market. Overall, these findings support the model's relevance in understanding the influence of cryptocurrency market dynamics on investment outcomes.

Coefficient Analysis

Table 12. Coefficient Analysis

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	.413	.699		.591	.558
	Price Fluctuations	.282	.150	.276	1.875	.068
	Volatility Metrics	-.277	.119	-.348	-2.322	.026
	Market Swings	.186	.138	.203	1.347	.186
a. Dependent Variable: Broker Return in Investment Portfolio						

The coefficient analysis presented in Table 12 reveals the individual impact of the independent variables on Broker Return in Investment Portfolio. The constant term is 0.413, indicating a baseline return when all predictors are zero. Price Fluctuations positively influence broker returns, with a coefficient of 0.282, though it approaches significance with a p-value of 0.068. In contrast, Volatility Metrics exhibit a negative relationship, with a coefficient of -0.277 and a significant p-value of 0.026, indicating that higher volatility correlates with lower returns. Market Swings have a positive coefficient of 0.186, but their effect is not statistically significant ($p = 0.186$). This analysis underscores the complex dynamics between market factors and investment returns.

Discussion of the Findings

Price Fluctuations

The findings indicate a positive relationship between price fluctuations and broker returns, with an unstandardized coefficient of 0.282 ($p = 0.068$). This suggests that as price fluctuations increase, broker returns may also rise, albeit at a marginal level of significance. Similar findings are echoed in the study by Gandal et al. (2022), which highlights that incorporating cryptocurrencies into diversified portfolios can enhance returns despite inherent volatility. The positive correlation found here underscores the necessity for brokers to develop adaptive investment strategies that respond to price changes effectively. Conversely, Letho et al. (2022) found that while price fluctuations offer potential returns, they can also introduce substantial risks, particularly in emerging markets. This divergence emphasizes the complexity of managing investments in volatile environments like cryptocurrencies. The implication for brokers and investors in Tanzania is clear: robust risk management strategies should be implemented to navigate price volatility while capitalizing on potential gains. Furthermore, this discussion supports the tenets of Modern Portfolio Theory (MPT), which posits that the right mix of assets can optimize returns based on varying risk levels, affirming the importance of diversification strategies in crypto markets.

Volatility Metrics

The negative impact of volatility metrics on broker returns, as indicated by the coefficient of -0.277 ($p = 0.026$), illustrates a critical challenge for brokers managing cryptocurrency portfolios. This finding aligns with Corbet et al. (2020), who demonstrated that high volatility in cryptocurrency markets can lead to significant investment risks, necessitating advanced risk management strategies. The implication here is profound: brokers must not only monitor volatility closely but also develop strategies that mitigate its adverse effects on returns. In contrast, Ermek (2021) suggested that while volatility poses challenges, it also creates opportunities for diversification, which can enhance portfolio resilience. This differing perspective highlights that while volatility is often viewed negatively, it can also drive innovation in risk management strategies. For Tanzanian brokers, understanding the dual nature of volatility is crucial for developing effective investment strategies. The findings resonate with MPT's principles, reinforcing the notion that a diversified portfolio can help buffer against volatility, thereby enhancing overall investment performance while managing risk effectively.

Market Swings

The study's results suggest a positive, yet statistically insignificant, relationship between market swings and broker returns, with a coefficient of 0.186 ($p = 0.186$). This outcome indicates that while market swings can influence returns, the effect may not be substantial enough to warrant immediate action from brokers. Similar insights were found in Liu and Tsyvinski (2021), which highlighted the complexities of managing investments in response to market fluctuations. Their research indicated that brokers must be adaptive and responsive to changing market conditions to optimize returns. Conversely, Ermek (2021) noted that while market swings might pose challenges, they also offer opportunities for strategic investment adjustments. This dichotomy suggests that brokers need to remain vigilant and flexible to exploit favorable market conditions. For brokers in Tanzania, the findings underscore the importance of not only monitoring market swings but also employing strategic adjustments based on market conditions. Moreover, the connection to MPT is relevant, as it reinforces the idea that effective diversification and strategic asset allocation can mitigate the risks associated with market swings, thereby enhancing overall portfolio performance.

Conclusion, and recommendations

Conclusion

This study offers significant insights into how price fluctuations, volatility metrics, and market swings impact broker returns in Tanzania's cryptocurrency market. The findings affirm the principles of the Risk-Return Trade-Off model, which asserts that brokers must balance the inherent risks of cryptocurrency investments with the potential for high returns. Furthermore, this research contributes to Modern Portfolio Theory by underscoring the necessity of diversification as a risk management strategy, validating its application in volatile markets.

Practically, the insights from this study can aid brokers in refining their investment strategies and developing robust risk management frameworks, allowing them to better navigate the complexities of cryptocurrency trading. By linking these findings back to the study's objectives, it is clear that effective management of market dynamics is essential for maximizing returns. This research not only enhances theoretical understanding but also equips practitioners with actionable strategies to improve investment performance in the evolving landscape of cryptocurrency, reinforcing the significance of adaptive investment approaches in high-volatility environments.

Recommendations

To enhance the effectiveness of cryptocurrency investments in emerging economies, this study recommends that brokers develop robust risk management strategies that incorporate insights from volatility metrics and market swings. Additionally, implementing educational programs for brokers focused on the implications of price fluctuations can empower them to make informed investment decisions. There is also a pressing need for regulatory frameworks that address the challenges posed by the cryptocurrency market. Establishing clear guidelines to promote transparency and protect investors can help mitigate the risks associated with high volatility. Collaborative efforts between governments and financial institutions are essential to create a supportive environment that encourages responsible cryptocurrency usage, contributing to market stability. Such frameworks can facilitate greater participation from traditional investors, ultimately aiding in the maturation of the cryptocurrency market in emerging economies like Tanzania. Expanding these recommendations to encompass broader implications will ensure a more sustainable and secure investment landscape for all stakeholders involved.

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